

Stereochemistry of α -Oximino- β -Substituted Hydrazones of Acetoacetarylamides and their Palladium Chelates*

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Stereospecific formation of only one *anti*-isomer is shown from the study of the stereochemistry of α -oximino- β -substituted hydrazones and their palladium chelates.

Although isomerism among compounds containing nitrogen, like oximes, hydrazones, osazones, diazo, azo, and azoxy compounds etc., are known quite a long time, the study of the isomerism in vicinal oxime-hydrazones, except the work of Taylor *et al.*¹, seems lacking. An attempt has therefore been made in this communication to study stereochemical possibilities in the oxime-hydrazones² of acetoacetarylamides.

Since the carbonyl group in α -oximino-acetoacetarylamides possesses environmental dissymmetry, the geometrical isomers (I) and (II) are expected to be obtained provided that no steric change at α -oximino group occurs and the isomers (III) and IV would be possible in the event of such a change.

(I)

(*anti*-form)

(II)

(*amphi*-form)

(III)

(*amphi*-form)

(IV)

(*syn*-form)

[where R = aryl group; R' = CONH₂, -CSNH₂, -COPh, -COC₆H₄(OH) (*ortho*)].

Contrary to this expectation, different isomers could not be obtained even though several variations were made in the process of preparation and crystallisation. In practice, a good yield of only one isomer could be realised in all the cases².

To assign the configuration to the product obtained, the following points have been taken into account:

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1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 257.

2. Patel and Mankad, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 841.

(i) When substituted hydrazines react on α -oximino-acetoacetylarnides, the α -oximino group is not replaced. This shows³ that the hydroxyl group does not fall in the proximity of the carbonyl group. This means that α -oximino-acetoacetylarnides have *anti*-acetyl structure.

(ii) Further, the ketone oximes having the group

with this configuration in open aliphatic compounds react with alkali providing yellow salts and with ferrous salts yielding blue or violet complexes⁴. The α -oximino-acetoacetylarnides also show similar colour reactions which indicate the presence of the same group.

(iii) The tendency of the incoming hydrazino group is to occupy less-hindered position in a molecule, as previously reported⁵. This is also observed during the formation of α -oximinohydrazones. The incoming group occupies *syn*-methyl position. Had this incoming group occupied *anti*-methyl position as in (IV), the product in *syn*-form would have invariably yielded cyclised products such as 1,3,4-tri-substituted or 3,4-di-substituted 1,2,5-triazole⁶⁻⁷ or 4-oximino-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone⁸ with or without a substituent at position 1. As no such products are formed, structure (IV) is discarded.

(iv) Configurations (II) and (III) are *amphi*-type and it is known from the study of dioximes that the products with *amphi*-structure are generally least stable. Moreover, if at all these are formed, product (II) would have cyclised to a triazole and product (III) to a 1,2,5-oxadiazole. Since such compounds have not been obtained during preparation, structures (II) and (III) are discarded.

(v) The oxime-hydrazones under the present study are found to be stable and remain unchanged during purification process and on heating in an oven below their melting points.

(vi) The oxime-hydrazones behave as monobasic acids and form metal complexes with the salts of transitional metals such as Pd, Ni, Cu, and Co. Thus the behaviour is similar to that of *anti-vic* dioximes.

Thus *anti* configuration, as shown in (I), is assigned to the compounds under reference.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chelation

For further confirmation, the compounds were tested for their chelation ability. Palladium forms golden yellow to deep red products; copper forms greenish to

3. Forster and Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2294.

4. Fiegl *et al.*, "Organic Analytical Reagents", edited by Welcher, Vol. III, D. Van Nostrand Company, 1962, p 272.

5. Patel and Mankad, under publication.

6. Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1889, 21, 2769.

7. Ponsic, *Gazzetta*, 1890, 20, 280.

8. Knorr and Reuter, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 1175.

brown compounds; ferric iron forms with thiosemicarbazones violet-red compounds; nickel forms light yellow to red compounds and cobalt forms chocolate products. These colour reactions are characteristic of chelate compounds.

For having substantiative experimental evidence, several palladium chelates, listed in Tables I-IV, were prepared by treating aqueous solution of palladium chloride, acidified with HCl (conc.), with ethanolic solution of α -oximino- β -substituted hydrazones and their m.p.s, composition, and solubility were determined. These are insoluble in water but soluble in chloroform, indicating their chelation.

TABLE I

Chelates of α -oximino-acetoacetylarnide semicarbazones.

No. Semicarbazones.	M.P. (decomp.)	Colour.	Formula.	%Palladium.		%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1 A-p-toluidide	270°	Golden yellow	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₁₀ Pd	16.12	16.20	21.30	21.25
2 A-o-chloroanilide	280°	Bright yellow	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₁₀ Cl ₂ Pd	15.12	15.25	19.05	20.01
3 A-m-chloroanilide	268°	Do	"	15.16	"	20.20	"
4 A-p-chloroanilide	270°	Golden yellow	"	15.22	"	19.90	"
5 A-o-anisidide	265°	Orange-yellow	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₁₀ Pd	15.60	15.45	20.20	20.27
6 A-p-anisidide	267°	Red	"	15.37	"	20.30	"
7 A-m-xylylide	> 360°	Golden yellow	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ O ₆ N ₁₀ Pd	15.42	15.54	20.45	20.38
8 A-2,4-dimethoxyanilide	269°	Red	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ O ₁₀ N ₁₀ Pd	14.00	14.21	18.63	18.65
9 A-p-phenetidide	263°	Red	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ O ₆ N ₁₀ Pd	15.02	14.85	19.42	19.48

(A denotes α -oximino-acetoacet-).

TABLE II

Chelates of α -oximino-acetoacetylarnide thiosemicarbazones.

No. Thiosemicarbazones.	M.P. (decomp.)	Colour.	Formula.	%Palladium.		%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1 A-p-toluidide	200°	Deep red	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Pd	15.39	15.45	20.20	20.27
2 A-o-chloroanilide	> 360°	"	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₁₀ Cl ₂ S ₂ Pd	14.82	14.58	19.09	19.14
3 A-m-chloroanilide	207°	Orange	"	14.52	"	19.20	"
4 A-p-chloroanilide	210°	Red	"	14.55	"	19.10	"
5 A-o-anisidide	195°	"	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₁₀ S ₂ Pd	14.80	14.77	19.28	19.37
6 A-p-anisidide	222°	"	"	14.80	"	19.27	"
7 A-m-xylylide	286°	Deep red	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Pd	14.78	14.84	19.42	19.48
8 A-2,4 dimethoxyanilide	232°	Orange	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ O ₆ N ₁₀ S ₂ Pd	13.70	13.63	17.78	17.89
9 A-p-phenetidide	215°	Orange-red	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ O ₆ N ₁₀ S ₂ Pd	14.17	14.21	18.78	18.65

TABLE III

Chelates of α -oximino-acetoacetylarnide benzoylhydrazones.

No.	Benzoylhydrazones.	M.P. (decomp.)	Colour.	Formula.	%Palladium.		%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	A-p-toluidide	> 360°	Golden yellow	C ₃₈ H ₃₄ O ₆ N ₆ Pd	13.74	13.67	14.30	14.25
2	A-o-chloroanilide	320°	Bright yellow	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₆ Cl ₂ Pd	12.04	12.97	13.80	13.63
3	A-m-chloroanilide	305°	Do	"	12.92	"	13.78	"
4	A-p-chloroanilide	325°	Do	"	12.83	"	13.70	"
5	A-o-anisidide	300°	Golden yellow	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ O ₈ N ₆ Pd	13.30	13.12	13.85	13.76
6	A-p-anisidide	327°	Orange	"	13.16	"	13.72	"
7	A-m-xylidide	330°	Golden yellow	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ O ₆ N ₆ Pd	13.31	13.19	13.91	13.86
8	A-p-phenetidide	320°	Orange-red	C ₃₈ H ₃₆ O ₆ N ₆ Pd	12.55	12.69	13.27	13.32

TABLE IV

Chelates of α -oximino-acetoacetylarnide salicylhydrazones.

No.	Salicylhydrazones.	M.P. (decomp.)	Colour.	Formula.	%Palladium		%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	A-p-toluidide	310°	Golden yellow	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ O ₇ N ₆ Pd	13.05	13.12	13.72	13.76
2	A-o-chloroanilide	312°	Bright yellow	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂ Pd	12.45	12.50	13.30	13.12
3	A-m-chloroanilide	305°	Do	"	12.41	"	13.24	"
4	A-p-chloroanilide	314°	Golden yellow	"	12.43	"	13.04	"
5	A-o-anisidide	295°	Do	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ O ₁₀ N ₆ Pd	12.54	12.63	13.40	13.26
6	A-p-anisidide	312°	Red	"	12.58	"	13.18	"
7	A-m-xylidide	308°	Golden yellow	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ O ₇ N ₆ Pd	12.61	12.70	13.38	13.32
8	A-2,4 dimethoxyanilide	303°	Red	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ O ₁₂ N ₆ Pd	11.61	11.67	12.35	12.25
9	A-p-phenetidide	296°	Red	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ O ₁₀ N ₆ Pd	12.15	12.22	12.95	12.84

DISCUSSION

At this stage it is necessary to consider the question of functional groups involved in ring formation and its size. Apparently, the functional groups that can take part in chelation are:

Out of these three possibilities, possibility (I) is upheld and (II) and (III) are discarded on considering the following points:

(i) Chaplin and Hunter⁹ have clearly shown that -NHR group of acetoacetarylamides does not participate in chelation as evinced from structure (IV). The same observation is confirmed by them in the hydrogen chelate of salicylanilide (V).

(IV)

(V)

This makes possibility(III) untenable.

(ii) Possibility (II) would lead to a six-membered, co-ordinated ring structure because OH of the oximino group falls in the proximity of the carbonyl oxygen. Taylor and Ewbank¹⁰ with reference to β -benzil monoxime:

have shown that compounds having such ring structures do not form complexes with metal salts.

Since the compounds of the present study yield metal complexes, possibility (II) becomes untenable.

(iii) Desai *et al.*¹¹ studied the formation of metal chelates of α -oximino-acetoacetarylamides and offered structure (VI)

(VI)

in which the oximino group was shown to assume the structure $=\overset{\nearrow}{N}$, similar to that observed in vicinal dioximes and analogous compounds^{12,13}.

9. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 484.

10. *Ibid.*, 1926, 2818.

11. Desai *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1964, 33, 613.

12. Brady and Muers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1609.

13. Dave and Talati, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 578.

This fact has led to the conclusion that the functional groups $=N.NHR'$ and $=NOH$ (in modified structural form) participate in the formation of a five-membered ring:

In order to determine the configuration of palladium chelates, magnetic property of the representative chelates was studied qualitatively by Gouy's magnetic balance and these were found to be diamagnetic. Hence these have been assigned square planar configuration. Other stereochemical possibilities arising from environmental dissymmetry are under study.

From this overall study it is apparent that formation of substituted hydrazones from α -oximino-acetoacetylarnides is stereospecific, leading to only *anti*-isomer.

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